

A Multi-Departmental Satisfaction Evaluation of Office Staff Performance of San Isidro College: Building a Client-Centric Culture

Elven James S. Acal, MA ^{1a}, Evan P. Taja-on, MSc ^{2b}, Emeterio R. Millalos, Jr ^{1c}

¹Office of Student Affairs and Services, San Isidro College, Malaybalay City, Bukidnon, 8700

²Education Department, San Isidro College, Malaybalay City, Bukidnon, 8700

✉ ^aejacal@sic.edu.ph, ^betajaon@sic.edu.ph, ^cemillalos@sic.edu.ph

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ABSTRACT

The efficiency and effectiveness of a school's operations heavily depend on the quality of services provided by its office staff across various departments. This study seeks to fill this gap by evaluating the satisfaction of staff performance, offering a comprehensive analysis that identifies strengths and areas needing improvement. By providing actionable insights, the research aims to enhance service delivery and contribute to the overall success of the institution. The study employed a descriptive research design to evaluate student satisfaction with office staff performance using an adopted questionnaire at San Isidro College, using a convenience sampling technique to survey 705 college students. The results indicated that students at San Isidro College are generally satisfied with the respect shown by office staff but see room for improvement in staff eagerness and availability. The study underscores the importance of implementing strategies to enhance professional communication, streamline processes, ensure financial transparency, and cultivate a hospitable environment. These efforts will ultimately contribute to higher student satisfaction and a more supportive educational experience.

Keywords: *client-centric evaluation, multi-departmental evaluation, office staff, satisfaction evaluation*

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

The services provided by various departments within a school play a crucial role in maintaining the institution's operational efficiency and ensuring a positive environment for both staff and students (Ocampo et al., 2019). Monitoring these services is essential as it enables the identification of strengths and areas for improvement, thereby contributing to the overall performance and effectiveness of each department and the school as a whole (Miranda & Reyes-Chua, 2021). Effective staff services directly influence the satisfaction and productivity of the

entire school community, making their evaluation a fundamental aspect of institutional success (Rodriguez et al., 2018).

Despite the office staff's critical role, there exists a gap in quantitatively evaluating their performance, which often leads to baseless generalizations and assumptions about their efficiency (Aceron, 2019). Such generalizations can negatively impact staff morale and performance, as they need to reflect the work being done accurately (Özdemir, 2021). The study addresses the lack of empirical data on staff performance, seeking to provide a comprehensive and accurate evaluation that can inform better management and improvement strategies.

Conducting studies that quantify the performance of office staff is important as it provides objective data that can be used to enhance service delivery and support staff development (Ocampo et al., 2019; Miranda & Reyes-Chua, 2021). By comprehending the specific areas where staff excel and where they need support, institutions can implement targeted interventions that improve overall effectiveness (Gabinete et al., 2022). This intervention, in turn, has a significant impact on the institution's ability to achieve its goals and maintain a high standard of service.

The study aspires to address the empirical gap identified in the research by Gantalao et al. (2021), which highlighted the need for more detailed and quantitative assessments of office staff performance. The necessity for such a study is underscored by the need for accurate and reliable data to inform policy and practice within the school.

The study aims to systematically evaluate the satisfaction levels of office staff performance across multiple departments, providing a comprehensive analysis of their performance and identifying key areas for improvement.

Conceptual Framework

The study anchors on the Student-as-Partner (SaP) Framework (Millar et al., 2024), which emphasizes collaboration and partnership between students and staff in enhancing educational experiences and outcomes. This framework is significant for the study in incorporating student feedback into the evaluation of office staff performance. By viewing students as active partners rather than passive recipients, the framework supports the idea that student evaluations are vital in shaping the effectiveness and satisfaction of office staff performance. This collaborative approach ensures that the voices of students are integral in assessing and improving staff services, fostering a more inclusive and responsive educational environment.

Figure 1.
Schematic diagram of the study

The Student-as-Partner Framework provides a comprehensive understanding of how external evaluations and student perceptions influence office staff performance satisfaction. It highlights the importance of this feedback in creating a collaborative and supportive environment. It

underscores the critical role of student evaluations in shaping office performance and driving improvements in service delivery.

Statement of the Problem

The study evaluated the clients' satisfaction on the office staff performance and sought to provide actionable insights that can help improve staff services and, consequently, the overall performance of the institution. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the clients' satisfaction evaluation of the office staff performance?
2. What are the suggestions of the clients towards the improvement of the office staff performance?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study utilized a descriptive research design (Dulock, 1993) to evaluate the satisfaction with office staff performance at San Isidro College. Descriptive research is employed to systematically describe and interpret the current status of office staff performance as perceived by students. This design is appropriate for the study as it allows for a comprehensive analysis of students' assessments, providing detailed insights into the specific areas of staff performance that influence satisfaction.

Sample and Site Location

The study's respondents consist of 705 college students who are officially enrolled in the various courses offered at San Isidro College. The sample size is large enough to provide a comprehensive overview of student satisfaction with office staff performance, ensuring that the findings are representative of the broader student population. The study was conducted at San Isidro College, a private Catholic institution located in Malaybalay City, Bukidnon. The college offers a range of academic programs, providing a suitable setting for assessing the performance of office staff across different departments and student needs.

Sampling Technique and Research Instrument

The study employed convenience sampling (Sedgwick, 2013) to gather respondents. Convenience sampling involves selecting participants who are readily available and willing to participate, making it an efficient method for collecting data from a large number of students. This approach was chosen because it ensures a broad representation of student opinions across various courses, thereby capturing a diverse range of perspectives on office staff performance at San Isidro College.

The research instrument used in the study was adopted from Gantalao et al. (2021). It was pilot-tested and achieved a Cronbach's alpha of 0.792, indicating good reliability. The instrument consists of a structured questionnaire designed to measure various aspects of office staff performance, ensuring that the data collected is both relevant and reliable for evaluating staff satisfaction.

Data Gathering Procedure

The data for this study was gathered through a survey method (Jamsen & Corley, 2007), which involved distributing the questionnaires to the participating students. Each participant was informed about the purpose of the study, and their consent was obtained before participation. Data privacy was strictly adhered to, ensuring that all personal information was kept confidential and used solely for research purposes. The survey was conducted over four (4) weeks, allowing sufficient time for students to provide thoughtful and comprehensive responses. The collected data was then compiled and prepared for analysis, ensuring that all responses were accurately recorded and stored securely.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics were employed to analyze the collected data. This method allowed for the summarization of the data, providing a clear and concise overview of student satisfaction levels with office staff performance. Measures such as mean and standard deviation were used to interpret the data, highlighting key trends and areas for improvement in staff services.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Satisfaction Evaluation of the Office Staff Performance

Table 1 presents the summary of the students' satisfaction evaluation regarding the office staffs' performance.

Table 1.
Student satisfaction evaluation of office staff (N=705)

Item	\bar{x}	S.D.	Q.I.
The staff shows respect to clients.	3.77	1.032	Satisfied
The staff are polite and courteous in handling my inquiries.	3.74	1.028	Satisfied
The staff listen attentively to our concerns.	3.73	1.028	Satisfied
The staff communicate clearly and effectively with us.	3.72	1.010	Satisfied
The staff are friendly and cheerful when they render service.	3.71	1.025	Satisfied
The staff maintain professional relationship with us.	3.70	1.020	Satisfied
The staff post written notices/signs that are informative, helpful and use good language.	3.70	0.993	Satisfied
The staff show competence and confidence with respect to their functions and roles.	3.70	0.996	Satisfied
The staff are helpful in guiding people to the office concerned.	3.69	1.003	Satisfied
The staff are resourceful in addressing our needs.	3.69	1.010	Satisfied
The staff observe the standard operating procedure (SOP) in releasing the request.	3.68	0.991	Satisfied
The staff post notices and signs that are clear and readable.	3.68	0.995	Satisfied
The staff are tactful in responding to our questions and requests.	3.68	1.025	Satisfied
The staff implement school's Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) in a firm, kind, and humane manner.	3.67	0.991	Satisfied
The staff are quick and efficient to handle questions.	3.67	1.004	Satisfied
The staff are responsive to our needs and concerns.	3.67	1.009	Satisfied
The staff are willing to handle inquiries.	3.66	1.001	Satisfied
The staff greet us consistently when we go to their office.	3.65	1.031	Satisfied
The staff are eager to assist and help us.	3.63	0.990	Satisfied
The staff make themselves available to us even if they have an on-going task or work.	3.63	1.014	Satisfied
Overall Satisfaction	3.69	0.871	Satisfied

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As presented in Table 1, the highest evaluation score among the questions indicates that "*The staff shows respect to clients*" with a qualitative interpretation of "*satisfied*." The result suggests that students feel acknowledged and valued by the office staff, which is a crucial aspect of customer service and positively impacts their overall experience (Perez & Ilagan, 2020). On the other hand, the lowest evaluation scores are for the questions stating, "*The staff is eager to assist and help us*" and "*The staff makes themselves available to us even if they have an ongoing task or work*," both interpreted as "*satisfied*." The result indicates that while students generally appreciate the staff's respect, there is a noticeable gap in perceived eagerness and availability, which could affect the timeliness and efficiency of service delivery (Ibo, 2019; Sarsale, 2020).

The overall satisfaction of the students, as presented in Table 1, is "*satisfied*." This overall rating suggests that, on average, the students have a positive perception of the office staff's performance (Gabinete et al., 2022). However, the uniform rating across different aspects indicates areas where improvements can be made to elevate satisfaction levels from merely "*satisfied*" to "*very satisfied*." This result is crucial as it highlights the need for targeted improvements in specific service aspects, such as increasing staff availability and eagerness to assist, to enhance the overall service experience for students (Ocampo et al., 2019; Miranda & Reyes-Chua, 2021).

Suggestions of the Students

Matrix 1 summarized the students' suggestions towards the improvement of the office staff performance.

Matrix 1.

Summary of the students' suggestions.

Theme	Sub-theme	Sample Statements
Professional Communication	Be Polite	" <i>be more polite</i> " (S-235)
	Be Approachable	" <i>I hope the staff is more on approachable [sic]... sometimes pag badtrip sila kahit mag tatanong lang magagalit...</i> " (S-551) (" <i>I hope the staff is more approachable...sometimes is they are not in a good mood, if you ask a question, they get angry...</i> ")
	Be Respectful	" <i>...some even scolded for some errors and even decline our request. The tone and response are not also quite respectful. I know how to respect them yet they think that I am JUST a student that they can look down on...</i> " (S-114)
	Clarity	" <i>...sometimes they are not straight to the point on what they are meant to be understood by clients [sic]...</i> " (S-61)
Efficiency and Transparency	Establishment of Student Portal	" <i>...establish a student portal website wherein the student's information is accessible...it would be more efficient for faculty and instructors to upload their computed grades and the students to view and access their Academic grades inside the student portal...</i> " (S-145)
	Give Attention to Important Matters	" <i>...give much attention to student who have important matter to the staff...</i> " (S-301)
	Financial Transparency	" <i>...using semestral report of the finances so that we students will know the whereabouts of the money we paid</i> " (S-13)
	Add more Cashiers	" <i>...my suggestion is to add one more Cashier in time of exam...because pay during that time</i> " (S-110)
	Improve Client Transactions	" <i>Please do improve sa inyung pag entertain sa inyung mga students</i> " (S-55) (" <i>Please do improve on how you entertain your students</i> ")

Hospitality

“...I was dismayed with one on your personnel...for being not hospitable to those who ask for their assistance which I myself experienced not just once but thrice.” (S-112)

As presented in Matrix 1, the overarching theme of *Professional Communication* encompasses sub-themes like *politeness, approachability, respectfulness, and clarity*. These sub-themes reveal that students value courteous and respectful interactions, indicating that these aspects significantly impact their satisfaction with staff performance (Ocampo et al., 2019; Limama et al., 2022). Students' emphasis on clarity and approachability suggests that effective communication and a welcoming demeanor are critical factors in their assessment of staff services (Java, 2020). This insight is pivotal for staff training and development, emphasizing the need to enhance communication skills to improve student interactions (Mostaza et al., 2019).

The overarching theme of *Efficiency and Transparency* includes sub-themes such as the *establishment of a student portal, attention to important matters, financial transparency, adding more cashiers, and improving client transactions*. Students are keen on having streamlined processes and transparent operations, particularly concerning financial transactions and critical administrative tasks (Alegado, 2016; Ocampo et al., 2019). The call for more cashiers and a dedicated student portal underscores the need to reduce wait times and provide accessible information, which would greatly enhance the efficiency of office operations (Miranda & Reyes-Chua, 2021). Addressing these suggestions would not only improve student satisfaction but also optimize administrative workflow.

The theme of *Hospitality* in the student suggestions highlights the importance of a welcoming and supportive environment within the administrative offices (Perez & Ilagan, 2020). Students' emphasis on hospitality suggests that they value a warm and helpful atmosphere, which can significantly enhance their overall experience (Ocampo et al., 2019). This insight stresses the need for staff to cultivate an inviting and supportive presence, making students feel comfortable and valued during their interactions (Arangote, 2018). Improving hospitality could lead to higher satisfaction levels, fostering a more positive and supportive educational environment.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The results indicated that students at San Isidro College are generally satisfied with the respect shown by office staff but see room for improvement in staff eagerness and availability. While the overall satisfaction rating is "*satisfied*," there is a clear opportunity to enhance specific aspects of service delivery to increase overall satisfaction. Addressing these areas will be crucial for improving the efficiency and effectiveness of staff performance.

Furthermore, student suggestions centered on *Professional Communication* and *Efficiency Transparency* highlight the need for polite, approachable, and clear communication, as well as streamlined processes and transparent operations. These findings suggest that students value courteous interactions and efficient service delivery, which are critical for their overall satisfaction. The emphasis on establishing a student portal and adding more cashiers indicates a desire for more accessible and efficient administrative support. Additionally, the theme of *Hospitality* underscores the importance of creating a welcoming and supportive environment within the administrative offices. Students' focus on hospitality highlights the need for staff to be warm and helpful, which

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can greatly enhance the overall student experience. By addressing these suggestions, San Isidro College could significantly improve student satisfaction with office staff performance.

In conclusion, the study's findings reveal that while students are generally satisfied with the office staff's respectfulness, there are notable areas for improvement in eagerness to assist and availability. Enhancing professional communication, efficiency, transparency, and hospitality is key to elevating overall satisfaction levels. Addressing these areas will not only improve the performance of office staff but also contribute to a more positive and supportive educational environment at San Isidro College.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the study's results, it is recommended that San Isidro College implement regular training sessions focused on customer service skills, emphasizing the importance of readiness and availability. Additionally, a system to monitor and manage staff workload could be introduced to ensure that staff can be more accessible to students, even during busy periods. Developing a reward and recognition program for staff who demonstrate outstanding readiness to assist and availability will also motivate others to improve their performance.

Improving professional communication is essential for better student interactions. Conducting workshops on effective communication skills, focusing on politeness, approachability, respectfulness, and clarity, would be beneficial. Staff could be encouraged to seek feedback from students regularly to understand their communication needs better and adjust their approach accordingly. Developing clear communication guidelines and standards that all staff members are required to follow will ensure consistency and quality in interactions. Streamlining processes and increasing transparency are crucial for efficient service delivery. Establishing a student portal will provide easy access to important information and services, reducing the need for in-person visits and wait times. Increasing the number of cashiers during peak hours will also help reduce wait times and improve the efficiency of financial transactions. Ensuring financial transparency by regularly updating students on the status of their transactions and any changes to policies or procedures will build trust and clarity.

Fostering a welcoming and supportive environment is important for enhancing student satisfaction. Training staff to create a hospitable atmosphere by being warm, friendly, and supportive in all interactions will make a significant difference. Implementing feedback mechanisms for students to provide suggestions and report their experiences with staff will foster a culture of continuous improvement. Designing office spaces to be more inviting and comfortable will ensure that the physical environment also contributes to a welcoming experience. Surveying additional stakeholders is essential for a comprehensive evaluation. Extending the evaluation to include other stakeholders, such as parents, alumni, and faculty, will provide a broader understanding of office staff performance from different perspectives. The feedback from these stakeholders can be used to identify additional areas for improvement and develop targeted interventions.

Further studies are recommended to explore the long-term impact of the implemented recommendations on student satisfaction and staff performance. Investigating the specific factors that contribute to perceived readiness and availability will provide deeper insights into how these aspects can be improved. Studying the relationship between office staff performance and overall

institutional success will examine how improvements in staff services translate to better educational outcomes. Additionally, conducting individual department studies will ensure that each department's performance is monitored properly and that specific issues are addressed effectively.

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